

An Investigation of Pronunciation Teaching Perceptions of In-Service Teachers

Halil ERCAN¹ & Mehmet DEMİREZEN²

¹ Corresponding Author, Atatürk Teacher Training Academy, Nicosia, NORTH CYPRUS

halil.ercan@aoa.edu.tr

ORCID: 0000-0001-5154-8234

² Hacettepe University, Ankara, TÜRKİYE

demmehmet2011@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0002-4061-4715

Article information

Submission	19/11/2025	Revision received	11/03/2026
Acceptance	03/04/2026	Publication date	19/04/2026

Keywords:

Teacher perceptions

English as a foreign language (EFL)

Teacher cognition

Pronunciation instruction

English language teaching (ELT)

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Öğretmen algıları

Yabancı dil olarak İngilizce (EFL)

Öğretmen bilişi

Telaffuz öğretimi

İngiliz dili öğretimi (ELT)

Abstract: Pronunciation is a fundamental aspect of language learning, yet it is often overlooked due to challenges such as inadequate training, limited class time, and a lack of resources. Understanding teachers' perspectives can help refine instructional approaches and lead to more effective pronunciation instruction. This study aimed to examine the perceptions of in-service English language teachers in North Cyprus regarding pronunciation instruction and its role in English language teaching (ELT). A quantitative research design was employed, and data were collected from 132 secondary and high school English language teachers who volunteered (non-probability sampling). The Pronunciation Teaching Perception Scale (PTPS) was used as the main data collection instrument. The data were analyzed using SPSS 24, employing descriptive statistics, independent samples t-tests, and one-way ANOVA. Findings revealed that teachers generally held positive perceptions of pronunciation instruction, particularly in using English for communication and in emphasizing pronunciation instruction. Teachers working in private schools, English-medium institutions, or those with Ph.Ds, international experience, and either low or high teaching experience showed significantly higher perception scores. These results offer valuable implications for teacher training, curriculum development, and pronunciation pedagogy in EFL contexts.

Görevdeki Öğretmenlerin Telaffuz Öğretimine İlişkin Algılarının İncelenmesi

Özet: Telaffuz, dil öğreniminin temel bir yönüdür, ancak yetersiz eğitim, sınırlı ders süresi ve kaynak eksikliği gibi zorluklar nedeniyle sıklıkla göz ardı edilir. Öğretmenlerin bakış açılarını anlamak, öğretim yaklaşımlarını iyileştirmeye ve daha etkili telaffuz öğretim yöntemlerine katkıda bulunmaya yardımcı olabilir. Bu çalışma, Kuzey Kıbrıs'taki hizmet içi İngilizce öğretmenlerinin telaffuz öğretimi ve İngilizce dil öğretimindeki rolü hakkındaki algılarını incelemeyi amaçlamıştır. Nicel bir araştırma tasarımı kullanılmış ve gönüllü katılımla (olasılıksız örnekleme) seçilen 132 ortaokul ve lise İngilizce öğretmeninden veri toplanmıştır. Ana veri toplama aracı olarak Telaffuz Öğretimi Algı Ölçeği (PTPS) kullanılmıştır. Veriler, betimsel istatistikler, bağımsız örneklem t-testleri ve tek yönlü ANOVA kullanan SPSS 24 kullanılarak analiz edilmiştir. Bulgular, öğretmenlerin özellikle iletişim için İngilizce kullanımı ve telaffuz öğretimine vurgu yapılması konusunda telaffuz öğretimine ilişkin genel olarak olumlu algılara sahip olduğunu ortaya koymuştur. Özel okullarda, İngilizce eğitim veren kurumlarda veya doktora derecesine, uluslararası deneyime ve düşük veya yüksek öğretim deneyimine sahip öğretmenlerde önemli ölçüde daha yüksek algı puanları görülmüştür. Bu sonuçlar, EFL bağlamlarında öğretmen eğitimi, müfredat geliştirme ve telaffuz pedagojisi için değerli çıkarımlar sunmaktadır.

To Cite This Article: Ercan, H., & Demirezen, M. (2026). An investigation of pronunciation teaching perceptions of in-service teachers. *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, 20(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19449260>

1. Introduction

When English as a Second Language (ESL) and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners are considered, pronunciation teaching is seen as a critical part of language education. To provide high-quality language education, pronunciation instruction must be integrated into the curriculum (Derwing & Munro, 2015). However, many educators nowadays struggle to address this issue in their language classes due to limited exposure to authentic language environments, minimal interaction with native speakers, and significant phonetic and phonological differences between English and the learners' native languages (Derwing & Munro, 2015; Thomson, 2018). Although pronunciation in language classes is critical for language acquisition, many language teachers neglect it (Saito, 2021).

It could be argued that the reason for this case is a lack of formal training in pronunciation pedagogy for language teachers. Moreover, field research indicates that many teachers describe themselves as insufficient to teach pronunciation effectively due to a lack of training sessions, low confidence when teaching pronunciation features, and prior learning experiences that did not prioritize phonetic instruction (Couper, 2019; Tergujeff, Kuronen, and Kautonen, 2020). Furthermore, as noted by respected scholars Foote et al. (2016) and Murphy (2017), pronunciation instruction is not often emphasized in teacher and language education programs and policies. Consequently, this further complicates the issue.

On the other hand, as demonstrated by Segalowitz (2016) and Saito and Plonsky (2019), pronunciation difficulties are not limited to articulation problems but also reflect cognitive limitations in target language learning. Additionally, Saito, Trofimovich, and Isaacs (2017) point out that adult language learners tend to struggle much more to acquire the phonological features of the target language because their perceptual training is less adequate than that of young language learners. Therefore, it could be argued that explicit pronunciation instruction in the target language contributes to language learners' comprehension and fluency over time (Saito, 2021; Thomson & Derwing, 2015).

Various teaching approaches and techniques are suggested to improve pronunciation instruction in different contexts. The Grammar-Translation Method (GTM), as a traditional approach, is criticized for insufficient attention to the production of spoken language. On the other hand, communicative methods such as Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) and the Audio-Linguistic Method (ALM) are recommended, as they focus more on pronunciation practice and communicative competence than GTM (Larsen-Freeman, 2020; Levis, 2018). Furthermore, recent studies have shown that technological movements are facilitated by computer-assisted pronunciation instruction (CAPT), which has demonstrated significant improvements in language learners' pronunciation accuracy by providing immediate feedback and automated analysis (Liakin et al., 2017; McCrocklin, 2019).

In pronunciation instruction, the role of non-native English speakers (NNESTs) should be of great importance. Respectful studies have shown that NNESTs often face unique difficulties with their own pronunciation proficiency and potential biases stemming from learners and teaching environments (Nguyen et al., 2021). However, empirical studies also indicate that NNESTs can overcome the challenges encountered in teaching pronunciation when adequately trained (Nguyen et al., 2021). The findings of Tsang (2025) and Levis (2024), which examined both language teachers' and learners' attitudes toward pronunciation teaching and learning, suggested that although many educators acknowledge the importance of pronunciation instruction, they do not tend to prioritize teaching its features in their classes. In addition to this case, language learners in Munro and Derwing's (2020) study

reported that, in contexts with limited exposure to language, it becomes difficult to develop pronunciation skills.

To measure and reveal the exact pronunciation-learning perceptions of language learners, recent research has focused on developing valid and reliable tools to assess perceptions of pronunciation instruction. One significant contribution by Ercan and Gilanlioglu (2022) to the field of English language teaching was the development of the PTPS. On the other hand, to determine in-service teachers' perceptions of pronunciation teaching, another validated and reliable scale was developed by Ercan and Demirezen (2023). It is believed that, with these reliable tools, future research will be conducted to investigate the field of pronunciation teaching and learning much more effectively. Further, it is crucial to lead the way for in-service teachers by providing training on how they should perceive and implement pronunciation-teaching activities in their classes to teach more effectively using pedagogical strategies (Levis, 2022). As suggested by Levis (2022) and Setter and Jenkins (2023), innovative approaches and techniques, such as CAPT and AI-powered tools and platforms, are considered of great importance in language learning, as they can be used both in- and out-of-class to improve learners' pronunciation skills.

1.1. The Present Study

The main aim of this research was to determine the perceptions of in-service English language teachers regarding pronunciation teaching. The study aimed to answer the following research questions.

1. What level are teachers' perceptions of pronunciation?
2. Do teachers' pronunciation perceptions and sub-dimensions differ in terms of independent variables?
3. What is the relationship between teachers' living time in an English-speaking country and their perception of pronunciation and its sub-dimensions?
4. What is the relationship between teachers' perception of pronunciation and its sub-dimensions, and the time they have lived in a country with a different culture?
5. Is there a difference in the pronunciation perceptions of teachers regarding the language of instruction of the school in which they work?

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

The present study used a quantitative technique, as suggested by Creswell (2018), to examine in-service English teachers' perceptions of pronunciation teaching in their classes. This design was considered particularly suitable for revealing how language teachers' perceptions of pronunciation teaching differ across their classes and for providing generalizable findings. To obtain valid and reliable data, the survey (PTPS) was developed by Ercan and Demirezen (2023).

2.2. Participants

The participants in the study were 132 English language teachers from both public and private schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education (MonE) in North Cyprus. They were the in-service language teachers who taught in both Turkish- and English-medium settings. Their ages ranged from 20 to over 50 years. They had a wide range of cultural backgrounds. A nonprobability sampling method (Creswell, 2018) was used to select participants based on their suitability and willingness to participate in the study. Further details regarding the participants of the study are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 1.

Demographics of Teachers

		<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Gender	Female	104	78.8
	Male	28	21.2
Education	BA	64	48.5
	MA	51	38.6
	PhD	17	12.9
	0-5	23	17.4
Experience	6-10	26	19.7
	11-14	28	21.2
	15 and over	55	41.7
School	Public	80	60.6
	Private	52	39.4
Language of Instruction	Turkish Medium	37	28.0
	English Medium	95	72.0
	Turkish	111	84.1
Native Language	English	11	8.3
	Other	10	7.6
	Yes	54	40.9
Lived in an English-speaking country	No	78	59.1
	Yes	63	47.7
Different culture	Yes	63	47.7
	No	69	52.3

2.3. Data Collection

The data were collected through the PTPS, developed by Ercan and Demirezen (2023), with a Cronbach's Alpha of .924. The overall scale, as confirmed by the Exploratory Factor Analyses, consisted of 24 items and 5 factors. The confirmatory factor analysis of the scale yielded a value of 1.314.

2.4. Data Analysis

The data obtained by PTPS were entered into SPSS 24 for further analysis. First, descriptive statistics were calculated to summarize the participants' demographic characteristics. Then, to assess the distribution of the data, Skewness and Kurtosis values were examined and found to be within the acceptable range of ± 1 . It was gathered that the obtained data met the homogeneity criterion (Hair et al., 2010). For inferential analysis, independent-samples t-tests were used to compare differences between independent groups, such as gender and school type. For comparisons involving three or more groups, one-way ANOVA was conducted. When significant differences were identified, pairwise comparisons were performed using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test, assuming homogeneity of variances. The graphs in the study were generated in R (v4.5.2) using the rstatix, effect size, ggplot2, and ggpubr packages (Wickham, 2016; Ben-Shachar et al., 2020; Kassambara, 2023; Kassambara, 2026).

3. Findings

The main aim of this study was to examine language teachers' perceptions of pronunciation instruction. The findings are presented in separate tables below, and some key findings are supported by three box plot figures. Finally, the findings are discussed in relation to those of reputable studies in the literature, and the paper concludes with a conclusion section. Table 2 below presents the PTPS descriptive analysis and homogeneity results. The PTPS scale consists of five sub-dimensions. Since it is a 5-point Likert scale, the lowest score on the overall scale and each sub-dimension is 1, and the highest is 5. The first factor, English use in the communication dimension, had a mean score of 3.87, indicating a high perception

level and the highest average. The second factor, Efforts to improve pronunciation skills, is at a good (high) level, with a mean of 3.41. Factor three: Focus on grammar and sentence structure showed a moderate level of perception, with a mean score of 3.33. Factor four: Pronunciation teaching style was perceived at a moderate level with a mean of 3.29, but it was the factor with the lowest perception among all factors. The fifth factor, emphasis on pronunciation teaching, was perceived as good (high) with a mean of 3.68 among English teachers. When the overall mean score of the PTPS scale is analyzed, it shows that English teachers had a good level of perception of pronunciation teaching, with a mean score of 3.54. Skewness and kurtosis values for all sub-dimensions of the PTPS scale were within ± 1 and showed a homogeneous distribution (Hair et al., 2010).

Table 2.

PTPS Descriptive Analysis and Homogeneity Results

	N	\bar{x}	σ	Skewness	Kurtosis
F1. Using English for communication	132	3.87	.883	-.760	.228
F2. Efforts to improve pronunciation skills	132	3.41	.931	-.422	-.331
F3. Focus on grammar and sentence structures	132	3.33	.807	-.121	-.469
F4. Pronunciation teaching style	132	3.29	.772	.040	-.475
F5. Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	132	3.68	.870	-.267	-.672
PTPS	132	3.54	.659	-.435	-.407

Considering the gender variable among language teachers, the scores for all sub-dimensions and PTPS are shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3.

A Gender Comparison of English Language Teachers' Perceptions of Pronunciation Teaching

	Group	N	\bar{x}	σ	t	df	p	Cohen's d
F1. Using English for communication	Female	104	3.939	.899	1.583	130	.116	.337
	Male	28	3.642	.797				
F2. Efforts to improve pronunciation skills	Female	104	3.373	.974	-.938	130	.350	.199
	Male	28	3.559	.748				
F3. Focus on grammar and sentence structures	Female	104	3.372	.805	.972	130	.333	.207
	Male	28	3.205	.8194				
F4. Pronunciation teaching style	Female	104	3.324	.802	.941	130	.349	.200
	Male	28	3.169	.649				
F5. Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	Female	104	3.745	.872	1.475	130	.143	.314
	Male	28	3.473	.8425				
PTPS	Female	104	3.568	.679	.901	130	.369	.191
	Male	28	3.442	.577				

Note. Cohen's d values are reported as absolute values.

There was no significant difference between English language teachers' perceptions of pronunciation teaching in terms of gender in all sub-dimensions and therefore in the overall scale ($p > .05$). Although no significant differences were observed by gender, Cohen's d effect sizes are negligible. As for the education level of language teachers, the scores for all sub-dimensions and PTPS are shown in Table 4 below. In terms of educational level, only in the dimension of the emphasis on pronunciation teaching, it was seen that English teachers with Ph.D degrees showed a significant difference compared to English teachers with Master's degrees, and it was seen that Ph.D graduates gave more importance to pronunciation teaching ($p < .05$) (see Figure 2). Regarding this difference, the effect size was moderate ($\eta^2 = .06$). However, the level of education did not lead to a significant difference in the other sub-dimensions and, consequently, in the overall scale for pronunciation teaching ($p > .05$).

Table 4.

Education Level Comparison of English Language Teachers' Perceptions of Pronunciation Teaching

	Group	N	\bar{x}	σ	Mean Square	F	p	η^2	LSD
F1. Using English for communication	BA	64	3.882	.883	1.947	2.551	.082	.038	
	MA	51	3.732	.946	.763				
	PHD	17	4.284	.529					
F2. Efforts to improve pronunciation skills	BA	64	3.411	.896	.237	.270	.764	.004	
	MA	51	3.366	.970	.878				
	PHD	17	3.558	.984					
F3. Focus on grammar and sentence structures	BA	64	3.410	.801	1.438	2.245	.110	.034	
	MA	51	3.372	.799	.640				
	PHD	17	2.955	.801					
F4. Pronunciation teaching style	BA	64	3.296	.747	.002	.004	.996	0	
	MA	51	3.289	.863	.607				
	PHD	17	3.279	.598					
F5. Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	BA	64	3.722	.833	2.994	4.145	.018*	.060	PhD>MA
	MA	51	3.485	.910	.722				
	PHD	17	4.161	.706					
PTPS	BA	64	3.561	.655	.357	.818	.444	.013	
	MA	51	3.465	.736	.436				
	PHD	17	3.693	.359					

Considering the professional experience of in-service teachers, Table 5 below presents the significant scores for all sub-dimensions and PTPS.

Table 5.

English Language Teachers' Perceptions of Pronunciation Teaching in Terms of Professional Experience

	Group	N	\bar{x}	σ	Mean Sq.	F	p	η^2	LSD	
F1. Using English for communication	0-5	23	4.260	.789	6.159	9.397	.000*	.180	0-5>6-10 0-5>11-14	
	6-10	26	3.647	.991						.655
	11-14	28	3.273	.960						
	15 and over	55	4.130	.619						
F2. Efforts to improve pronunciation skills	0-5	23	3.492	.978	2.131	2.540	.059	.056		
	6-10	26	3.256	.932					.839	
	11-14	28	3.077	.861						
	15 and over	55	3.624	.907						
F3. Focus on grammar and sentence structures	0-5	23	3.423	.770	2.670	4.410	.005*	.094	0-5>11-14 6-10>11-14	
	6-10	26	3.336	.640						.605
	11-14	28	2.883	.695						
	15 and over	55	3.531	.872						
F4. Pronunciation teaching style	0-5	23	3.445	.839	.847	1.432	.236	.032		
	6-10	26	3.336	.908					.592	
	11-14	28	3.035	.731						
	15 and over	55	3.336	.682						
F5. Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	0-5	23	3.793	.800	2.423	3.374	.021*	.073	15+>6-10 15+>11-14	
	6-10	26	3.500	.927						.718
	11-14	28	3.339	.895						
	15 and over	55	3.909	.801						
PTPS	0-5	23	3.715	.598	2.616	6.820	.000*	.138	0-5>11-14 15+>6-10 15+>11-14	
	6-10	26	3.421	.752						.384
	11-14	28	3.131	.677						
	15 and over	55	3.734	.521						

There was a significant difference in the dimension of using English for communication, and it was observed that the perceptions of English teachers with 0-5 years of experience in using English for communication were higher than those of English teachers with 6-10 and 11-14 years of experience ($p < .05$). Effect size: large ($\eta^2 = .18$). In the Efforts to improve pronunciation skills dimension, the professional experience of English teachers did not create a significant difference ($p > .05$). Effect size: small ($\eta^2 = .056$). In the grammar and sentence structure dimension, there was a significant difference in professional experience: English teachers with 11-14 years of experience had lower scores than the other groups ($p < .05$). Effect size: medium ($\eta^2 = .094$). There was no significant difference in professional experience regarding the pronunciation-teaching style dimension ($p > .05$). The effect size was small ($\eta^2 = .032$). In the dimension of emphasis on pronunciation teaching, the scores of English teachers with 15 or more years of professional experience were significantly higher than those of teachers with 6-10 and 11-14 years of professional experience ($p < .05$). Effect size: medium ($\eta^2 = .073$). When English teachers' professional experience was compared with the PTPS scores, teachers with 0-5 years of experience had higher pronunciation perceptions than those with 11-14 years of experience ($p < .05$). Also, English teachers with 15 or more years of experience had higher pronunciation perceptions than those with 6-10 or 11-14 years of experience ($p < .05$). Effect size: medium ($\eta^2 = .138$) (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Box Plot of Education and Experience Sub-dimensions

The findings indicated that English teachers with a doctoral degree and extensive teaching experience (11–14 years or 15 years or more) had higher perceptions of pronunciation teaching. As shown in Table 6 below, scores for all sub-dimensions by school type are displayed.

Table 6.

English Language Teachers' Perceptions of Pronunciation Teaching in Terms of School Type

	Group	N	\bar{x}	σ	t	df	p	Cohen's d
F1: Using English for communication	Public	80	3.670	.859	-3.446	130	.001*	.614
	Private	52	4.192	.833				
F2: Efforts to improve pronunciation skills	Public	80	3.420	.813	.121	130	.904	.022
	Private	52	3.400	1.098				
F3: Focus on grammar and sentence structures	Public	80	3.296	.795	-.709	130	.480	.126
	Private	52	3.399	.830				
F4: Pronunciation teaching style	Public	80	3.159	.763	-2.487	130	.014*	.443
	Private	52	3.495	.749				
F5: Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	Public	80	3.506	.856	-3.062	130	.003*	.545
	Private	52	3.966	.822				
PTPS	Public	80	3.433	.691	-2.383	130	.019*	.424
	Private	52	3.708	.573				

Note. Cohen's d values are reported as absolute values.

In the sub-dimension of using English for communication, the perception level of English teachers working in private schools was significantly higher than that of teachers working in public schools ($p < .05$). Effect size: medium ($d = .614$). Efforts to improve pronunciation skills and to focus on grammar and sentence structure did not show a significant difference by school type ($p > .05$). Effect size: negligible ($d = .022$). Pronunciation teaching style and the emphasis on pronunciation teaching sub-dimensions show significant differences by school type, with private school ELT teachers' perceptions higher than those of public school ELT teachers ($p < .05$). Effect size: medium ($d = .545$). Pronunciation Teaching Perception shows significant differences among public and private school teachers by school type. Private school English teachers' perception of pronunciation teaching is higher than that of public school English teachers ($p < .05$). Effect size: small ($d = .424$).

Figure 2. Box Plot of School Type and Language of the Institution

When the medium of instruction is considered, all significant scores obtained regarding all sub-dimensions and PTPS are shown in Table 7 below.

Table 7.

English Language Teachers' Perceptions of Pronunciation Teaching in Terms of the Medium of Instruction

	Group	N	\bar{x}	σ	t	df	p	Cohen's d
F1: Using English for communication	Turkish Medium	37	3.081	.829	-7.778	130	.000*	1.507
	English Medium	95	4.186	.692				
F2: Efforts to improve pronunciation skills	Turkish Medium	37	2.959	.734	-3.649	130	.000*	.707
	English Medium	95	3.589	.944				
F3: Focus on grammar and sentence structures	Turkish Medium	37	2.885	.616	-4.267	130	.000*	.826
	English Medium	95	3.513	.807				
F4: Pronunciation teaching style	Turkish Medium	37	2.925	.761	-3.541	130	.001*	.686
	English Medium	95	3.434	.733				
F5: Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	Turkish Medium	37	3.000	.816	-6.495	130	.000*	1.258
	English Medium	95	3.955	.735				
PTPS	Turkish Medium	37	2.978	.675	-7.221	130	.000*	1.399
	English Medium	95	3.761	.507				

Note. Cohen's d values are reported as absolute values.

It was revealed that ELT teachers working in institutions where English was the medium of instruction had significantly higher scores in all sub-dimensions than those working in schools where Turkish was the medium of instruction ($p < .05$). The perceptions of ELT teachers working in English-medium institutions regarding pronunciation teaching were significantly higher than those of teachers working in Turkish-medium institutions ($p < .05$). Effect size: large ($d = 1.399$) (see Figure 2). To determine whether native language had any influence on perceptions of pronunciation instruction, Table 8 presents all scores collected by participants for all sub-dimensions. The only significant difference in mother tongue was in the sub-dimension of efforts to improve pronunciation skills, with Turkish native ELT teachers reporting higher efforts than native English teachers ($p < .05$). Effect size: small ($\eta^2 = .048$).

As for overseas experiences of the language teachers, Table 9 below displays all sub-dimensions and the obtained values. In all sub-dimensions except Efforts to improve pronunciation skills, the scores of ELT teachers living in an English-speaking country were significantly higher ($p < .05$). Effect size: negligible ($d = .052$). ELT teachers who lived in an English-speaking country had significantly higher perceptions of pronunciation teaching than ELT teachers who did not live in an English-speaking country ($p < .05$). Effect size: medium ($d = .621$) (see Figure 3). In terms of these results, living in an English-speaking country contributed positively to ELT teachers' use of English for communication, their focus on grammar and sentence structure, their pronunciation teaching style, and their

emphasis on pronunciation teaching. Further, Figure 3 presents a box plot illustrating the effect values of participants' experiences of living in an English-speaking country and in a different culture.

Table 8.

English Language Teachers' Perceptions of Pronunciation Teaching in Terms of the Mother Tongue

	Group	N	\bar{x}	σ	Mean Sq.	F	p	η^2	LSD
F1. Using English for communication	Turkish	111	3.879	.865	2.020	2.650	.074	.039	Turkish >English
	English	11	3.439	1.183	.762				
	Other	10	4.316	.454					
F2. Efforts to improve pronunciation skills	Turkish	111	3.483	.928	2.760	3.289	.040*	.048	
	English	11	2.742	1.068	.839				
	Other	10	3.366	.470					
F3. Focus on grammar and sentence structures	Turkish	111	3.358	.785	.251	.382	.684	.005	
	English	11	3.318	.902	.659				
	Other	10	3.125	.994					
F4. Pronunciation teaching style	Turkish	111	3.331	.770	.734	1.232	.295	.018	
	English	11	2.954	.797	.595				
	Other	10	3.225	.758					
F5. Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	Turkish	111	3.680	.857	1.180	1.572	.211	.023	
	English	11	3.409	1.026	.750				
	Other	10	4.07	.773					
PTPS	Turkish	111	3.56	.649	.915	2.141	.122	.032	
	English	11	3.15	.849	.427				
	Other	10	3.65	.397					

As shown in Figure 3, the results indicated a significant difference with a moderate effect size ($d = .621$) in favor of those living in English-speaking countries. Further, a significant difference with a moderate effect size ($d = .764$) in favor of those living in a different culture was found. This clearly demonstrates that living in an English-speaking country and in a different culture improves English teachers' perceptions of pronunciation teaching. In this regard, it has been observed that living in an English-speaking country and having experience living in different cultures positively influences the pronunciation teaching of language teachers.

Table 9.

Comparison of Teachers' Pronunciation Teaching Perceptions by Overseas Experience

	Group	N	\bar{x}	σ	t	df	p	Cohen's d
F1. Using English for communication	Yes	54	4.234	.733	4.102	130	.000*	.726
	No	78	3.628	.898				
F2. Efforts to improve pronunciation skills	Yes	54	3.441	1.021	.291	130	.771	.052
	No	78	3.393	.870				
F3. Focus on grammar and sentence structures	Yes	54	3.652	.844	3.936	130	.000*	.697
	No	78	3.118	.707				
F4. Pronunciation teaching style	Yes	54	3.490	.742	2.511	130	.013*	.445
	No	78	3.153	.767				
F5: Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	Yes	54	3.986	.876	3.411	130	.001*	.604
	No	78	3.480	.808				
PTPS	Yes	54	3.773	.556	3.510	130	.001*	.621
	No	78	3.380	.679				

Figure 3. Box Plot of Living in an English-speaking Country and Living in a Different Culture

The data on perceptions of pronunciation teaching by cultural experience are presented in Table 10 below. English language teachers who had lived in a different culture, used English for communication, and made efforts to improve pronunciation skills, focused on grammar and sentence structure, and emphasized pronunciation teaching sub-dimension were significantly higher than those who did not live in a different culture ($p < .05$). Effect size: small ($d = .346$). However, no significant difference in the living of different cultures in the Pronunciation teaching style sub-dimension was found ($p > .05$). In terms of these results, living in a different culture significantly increased ELT teachers' perception scores for pronunciation teaching ($p < .05$). The effect size was found to be medium ($d = .764$) (see Figure 3).

Table 10.

Comparison of Teachers' Pronunciation Teaching Perceptions by Cultural Experience

	Group	N	\bar{x}	σ	t	df	p	Cohen's d																																																												
F1. Using English for communication	Yes	63	4.209	.699	4.414	130	.000*	.769																																																												
	No	69	3.572	.929					F2 Efforts to improve pronunciation skills	Yes	63	3.579	.914	1.983	130	.049*	.346	No	69	3.260	.928	F3. Focus on grammar and sentence structures	Yes	63	3.631	.785	4.244	130	.000*	.740	No	69	3.068	.736	F4. Pronunciation teaching style	Yes	63	3.424	.765	1.907	130	.059	.332	No	69	3.170	.765	F5. Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	Yes	63	3.992	.809	4.064	130	.000*	.708	No	69	3.409	.834	PTPS	Yes	63	3.788	.528	4.384	130	.000*
F2 Efforts to improve pronunciation skills	Yes	63	3.579	.914	1.983	130	.049*	.346																																																												
	No	69	3.260	.928					F3. Focus on grammar and sentence structures	Yes	63	3.631	.785	4.244	130	.000*	.740	No	69	3.068	.736	F4. Pronunciation teaching style	Yes	63	3.424	.765	1.907	130	.059	.332	No	69	3.170	.765	F5. Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	Yes	63	3.992	.809	4.064	130	.000*	.708	No	69	3.409	.834	PTPS	Yes	63	3.788	.528	4.384	130	.000*	.764	No	69	3.316	.689								
F3. Focus on grammar and sentence structures	Yes	63	3.631	.785	4.244	130	.000*	.740																																																												
	No	69	3.068	.736					F4. Pronunciation teaching style	Yes	63	3.424	.765	1.907	130	.059	.332	No	69	3.170	.765	F5. Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	Yes	63	3.992	.809	4.064	130	.000*	.708	No	69	3.409	.834	PTPS	Yes	63	3.788	.528	4.384	130	.000*	.764	No	69	3.316	.689																					
F4. Pronunciation teaching style	Yes	63	3.424	.765	1.907	130	.059	.332																																																												
	No	69	3.170	.765					F5. Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	Yes	63	3.992	.809	4.064	130	.000*	.708	No	69	3.409	.834	PTPS	Yes	63	3.788	.528	4.384	130	.000*	.764	No	69	3.316	.689																																		
F5. Emphasis on pronunciation teaching	Yes	63	3.992	.809	4.064	130	.000*	.708																																																												
	No	69	3.409	.834					PTPS	Yes	63	3.788	.528	4.384	130	.000*	.764	No	69	3.316	.689																																															
PTPS	Yes	63	3.788	.528	4.384	130	.000*	.764																																																												
	No	69	3.316	.689																																																																

4. Discussion

Most importantly, the study affirms Ercan and Demirezen's (2023) findings by showing that contextual factors—such as school type, language of instruction, teaching experience, and international exposure—play a significant role in shaping pronunciation-related attitudes.

Teachers working in private schools and English-medium institutions, as well as those who had lived in English-speaking environments, showed significantly higher scores across nearly all PTPS sub-dimensions. These outcomes align with Levis's (2018) research, which emphasizes the role of immersive and intercultural experiences in enhancing teacher awareness and practice. Furthermore, the relatively moderate mean scores in sub-dimensions such as pronunciation teaching style and grammar-focused approaches suggested a persisting lack of pedagogical clarity or confidence, a challenge similarly reported by Couper (2019) and Murphy (2017). These issues may stem from insufficient emphasis on pronunciation pedagogy in teacher education, as discussed by Thomson and Derwing (2015) and confirmed by Saito and Plonsky's (2019) meta-analytical findings. Moreover, the fact that Ph.D holders and teachers with either very limited or extensive teaching experience scored higher suggests that both advanced academic knowledge and accumulated practical exposure may be key drivers of effective pronunciation instruction—a pattern previously noted in Ercan and Gilanlioğlu's (2022) study. This nuanced relationship between professional background and perception underscores the need for ongoing professional development and context-sensitive training. On the other hand, this study's findings highlight the complex yet critical role of pronunciation instruction in English language teaching as a foreign/second language, especially in EFL contexts such as North Cyprus. In-service English teachers generally demonstrated positive attitudes toward pronunciation instruction, particularly when they had advanced academically, had international experience, or worked in English-medium settings. The findings of a recent study by Kafes and Bayramoğlu (2025) parallel those of the present study, highlighting a significant mismatch between the cognitive beliefs about pronunciation teaching and the classroom practices of in-service and pre-service teachers. On the other hand, while teachers in the present study generally exhibited positive attitudes towards pronunciation teaching, the moderate scores observed in some pedagogical sub-dimensions indicate a similar gap between cognition and practice. This discrepancy has been widely attributed to contextual constraints and limited pedagogical training. Furthermore, both studies have confirmed that inadequate training in pronunciation pedagogy is a fundamental challenge.

5. Conclusion

This study aimed to reveal the perceptions of in-service English teachers regarding pronunciation instruction using PTPS, developed by Ercan and Gilanlioğlu (2022) and subsequently adapted for in-service teachers by Ercan and Demirezen (2023). The use of this validated tool was intended to enhance the study's reliability. It was also used to ensure continuity in the developing research environment on pronunciation instruction within the field of English teaching. As for the obtained results, it was revealed that while teachers generally held positive perceptions—especially in the sub-dimensions of using English for communication and placing emphasis on pronunciation instruction—there were still notable areas for development. The most notable finding from the study is that English-language institutions showed significantly higher perceptions across all sub-dimensions, with a very large effect size.

Additionally, experiential and environmental variables, such as working in private schools, living in English-speaking contexts, and exposure to diverse cultures, were found to increase teachers' perceptions significantly. Besides, the study highlights the cross-cultural exposure and the critical role of language. Moreover, the results also showed a non-linear relationship between working experience and perceptions of pronunciation teaching. However, both early-career (0-5 years) and experienced (15+ years) teachers reported higher perceptions of

pronunciation teaching than mid-career (11-14 years) teachers. Overall, the findings highlighted the importance of experiential and contextual factors rather than solely demographic variables, and they underscored the need to understand and improve pronunciation instruction practices in EFL contexts. By employing the PTPS (Ercan & Gilanloğlu, 2022; Ercan & Demirezen, 2023), this study provides a structured understanding of how demographic, educational, and contextual variables shape perceptions of pronunciation instruction. These results reinforce the call for more targeted and practical pronunciation pedagogy in teacher education programs and echo broader concerns in the literature about the persistent underrepresentation of pronunciation in curricula (Derwing & Munro, 2015; Foote et al., 2016). Moreover, this study underscores the importance of recognizing localized varieties of English within the broader World Englishes framework. In North Cyprus, English is not only a foreign language but also a contact language with distinctive phonological and lexical features, often referred to as Cypriot English. As English continues to evolve in localized contexts, teacher education programs must address the sociolinguistic reality of dialectal variation and its pedagogical implications. Acknowledging *Cypriot English* as a legitimate variety can foster greater linguistic awareness among teachers and learners, encourage tolerance of accent diversity, and support more inclusive approaches to pronunciation instruction. In line with global trends and technological developments, future research should explore the integration of AI-supported feedback tools and CAPT systems, which have shown promise in individualizing pronunciation instruction (McCrocklin, 2019; Setter & Jenkins, 2023). It is also recommended that national education stakeholders consider investing in sustained professional development programs that emphasize pronunciation teaching strategies, intercultural competence, and reflective practice. Ultimately, this study not only contributes to the local understanding of pronunciation pedagogy in ELT but also offers globally relevant insights for improving pronunciation instruction across diverse educational contexts.

Ethical Statement

This study received ethical approval from the Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee (BAYEK) of Eastern Mediterranean University (Approval Date: 22 April 2021; Issue No.: 91; Reference No.: ETK00-2021-0131) and was also approved by the TRNC Ministry of National Education (Approval Date: 11 January 2021; Issue No.: GOÖ.0.00-174/06-21/E.177; Reference No.: TTD.0.00-174/06-21/E.27).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

The data presented in this study are not publicly available due to confidentiality concerns. However, they may be obtained from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

Ben-Shachar, M. S., Lüdtke, D., & Makowski, D. (2020). Effect size: Estimation of effect size indices and standardized parameters. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 5(56), 2815. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.02815>

- Couper, G. (2019). Teachers' cognitions of corrective feedback on pronunciation: Their beliefs, perceptions and practices. *System*, 84, 41–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2019.04.003>
- Derwing, T. M., & Munro, M. J. (2015). *Pronunciation fundamentals: Evidence-based perspectives for L2 teaching and research (Vol. 42)*. John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Ercan, H., & Demirezen, M. (2023). Investigating in-service teachers' perceptions of pronunciation instruction in EFL contexts. *SAGE Open*, 13(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440231219065>
- Ercan, H., & Gilanlioglu, I. (2022). Development of a pronunciation teaching perception scale (PTPS) for preservice English language teachers. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 969917. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.969917>
- Foote, J. A., Trofimovich, P., Collins, L., & Urzúa, F. S. (2016). Pronunciation teaching practices in communicative second language classes. *The Language Learning Journal*, 44(2), 181–196. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09571736.2013.784345>
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Tatham, R. L. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis (7th ed.)*. Pearson Education.
- Nguyen, L. T., Hung, B. P., Duong, U. T. T., & Le, T. T. (2021). Teachers' and learners' beliefs about pronunciation instruction in tertiary English as a foreign language education. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 739842. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.739842>
- Kafes, H. & Bayramoğlu, B. (2025). EFL teachers' pronunciation cognition: Examining practice alignment and comparative cognitions of in-service and pre-service teachers. *Novitas-Royal*, 19(2), 69–92. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17050391>
- Kassambara, A. (2023). *rstatix: Pipe-friendly framework for basic statistical tests* (R package version 0.7.2). <https://rpkgs.datanovia.com/rstatix/>
- Kassambara, A. (2026). *ggpubr: 'ggplot2' based publication ready plots* (R package version 0.6.3). <https://rpkgs.datanovia.com/ggpubr/>
- Larsen-Freeman, D. (2020). *Techniques and principles in language teaching (4th ed.)*. Oxford University Press.
- Levis, J. M. (2018). *Intelligibility, oral communication, and the teaching of pronunciation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Levis, J. M. (2022). Future directions in pronunciation teaching: Where do we go from here? *Journal of Second Language Pronunciation*, 8(2), 146–161. <https://doi.org/10.1075/jslp.22049.lev>
- Levis, J. M. (2024). *Pronunciation in language teaching. Teaching pronunciation with confidence: A resource for ESL/EFL teachers and learners*. Iowa State University Digital Press.
- Liakin, D., Cardoso, W., & Liakina, N. (2017). Learning L2 pronunciation with a mobile speech recognizer: French /y/. *CALICO Journal*, 34(1), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2017.1312463>
- McCrocklin, S. M. (2016). Pronunciation learner autonomy: The potential of automatic speech recognition. *System*, 57(1), 25–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2015.12.013>
- Munro, M. J., & Derwing, T. M. (2020). Pronunciation instruction: Research to practice. In M. O'Brien & J. M. Levis (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 10th pronunciation in second language learning and teaching conference* (pp. 7–16). Iowa State University.
- Murphy, J. M. (2017). *Teacher training in the teaching of pronunciation*. In M. Reed & J. M. Levis (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of contemporary English pronunciation* (pp. 298–319). Routledge.
- Saito, K. (2021). *Effects of corrective feedback on second language pronunciation development*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108589789.020>

- Saito, K., & Plonsky, L. (2019). Effects of second language pronunciation teaching revisited: A proposed measurement framework and meta-analysis. *Language Learning*, 69(3), 652–708. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lang.12345>
- Saito, K., Trofimovich, P., & Isaacs, T. (2017). Using listener judgments to investigate linguistic influences on L2 comprehensibility and accentedness: A validation and generalization study. *Applied Linguistics*, 38(4), 439–462. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amv047>
- Segalowitz, N. (2016). Second language fluency and its underlying cognitive and social determinants. *International Review of Applied Linguistics in Language Teaching*, 54, 79–95. <https://doi.org/10.1515/iral-2016-9991>
- Setter, J., & Jenkins, J. (2023). Pronunciation in global English: Pedagogical implications. *World Englishes*, 42(1), 35–47. <https://doi.org/10.55606/jupensi.v5i3.6101>
- Tergujeff, E., Kuronen, M., & Kautonen, M. (2020). Kazoo training for L2 pronunciation practice and reduced foreign accentedness? *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching*, 14(3), 290–302. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17501229.2019.1586908>
- Thomson, R. I. (2018). High variability [pronunciation] training (HVPT): A proven technique every teacher should know. *Journal of Second Language Pronunciation*, 4(2), 208–231. https://languagelog.ldc.upenn.edu/myl/2018Thomson_HVPT.pdf
- Thomson, R. I., & Derwing, T. M. (2015). The effectiveness of L2 pronunciation instruction: A narrative review. *Applied Linguistics*, 36(3), 326–344. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/amu076>
- Tsang, A. (2025). EFL listening, pronunciation, and teachers' accents in the present era: An investigation into pre and in-service teachers' cognition. *Language Teaching Research*, 29(1), 199-220. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13621688211051>
- Wickham, H (2016). *ggplot2: Elegant graphics for data analysis*. Springer-Verlag.